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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
API	Application Programming Interface
CHIL	Controller Hardware in the Loop
CIM	Common Information Model
CM	Configuration Management
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DNS	Domain Name System
DoE	Department of Energy
DRTS	Digital Real-Time Simulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
HIL	Hardware in the Loop
HTD	Holistic Testing Procedure
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
ID	Identification
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technology
JaNDER	Joint Test Facility for Smart Energy Networks with Distributed Energy Resources
JRA	Joint Research Activity
PHIL	Power Hardware in the Loop
PV	Photovoltaic
PWM	Pulse-width Modulation
RI	Research Infrastructure
RTS	Real-time Simulator
SMB	Simulation Message Bus
SysML	Systems Modelling Language
uAPI	Universal Application Programming Interface
US	United States
VILLAS	Virtually Interconnected Laboratories for LArge systems Simulation/emulation
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

Executive Summary

One of the challenges associated with undertaking distributed experiments involving multiple Research Infrastructures is the complex and ever-changing nature of laboratory configurations. In order to repeat or replicate experiments, the identical configuration of systems and components is crucial; yet, research laboratories tend to be work-in-progress. Standard parameters are changed, and equipment and software are moved, updated or replaced. One of the learning experiences from ERIGrid 2.0 predecessor ERIGrid has been that this problem generates a lot of tedious manual work which is prone to human error.

One of the goals of this work has been to identify ways to automate configuration management, in ways that would reduce the manual effort associated with distributed multi-Research Infrastructures experiments while being implementable with the available resources in the project. This report presents the work towards this goal undertaken, specifically:

- *The development and selection of configuration management use cases specific to the needs of ERIGrid 2.0:* Working groups identified two primary types of use cases addressing static configuration (conveying pre-existing knowledge about a facility) and dynamic configuration (tracking configuration changes across time). Within this space, three potential use cases were identified, and one was selected as the most realistic from a perspective of enabling the broadest implementation across partners: The automated configuration of data exchanges between Research Infrastructures based on a global signal configuration.
- *The development of a configuration management workflow:* In an iterative process involving the developers of the three data transport packages used in ERIGrid 2.0, a workflow has been designed that accounts for different deployment structures (centralised, peer-to-peer and federated) and properties of these packages. The general concept is based on the automated generation of individual local signal configurations from a single global experiment configuration.
- *The definition of a standardised description of data exchanges between Research Infrastructures:* A working group has created a YAML-based definition of a global experiment configuration which defines signals, their exchange patterns between research infrastructures, and the data transport packages used for the actual exchange.
- *The creation and testing of three reference implementations.* As a proof-of-concept, the global signal configuration was used to configure each of the three data transport packages used in ERIGrid 2.0 (i.e., VILLASnode, JaNDER, and Lablink) and in combination with the uAPI.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This report aims to capture the joint system description specified in ERIGRID 2.0, along with the methodical and technical context of the automated configuration management solutions developed within the same task.

Efficiently managing configuration within a diverse distributed system poses a significant challenge. In ERIGRID 2.0, when integrating simulators and/or Research Infrastructures (RIs) from multiple organisations to conduct joint tests, it becomes essential to precisely determine, document, and potentially replicate the exact configuration of the distributed test setup. In a laboratory environment, various layers of configuration coexist. While some aspects, such as the overall system composition (e.g., grid topology and connected components), typically receive primary attention, other equally critical system configuration elements, including device characterisation and active operating modes, often go unnoticed despite their impact on experiment repeatability. Currently, the fragmented landscape of incomplete system descriptions and procedures necessitates a manual approach that is both laborious and susceptible to errors. The following topics are covered by this task:

- Development of a method for joint system description across domains and infrastructures whereas this activity will seek to leverage, combine and – if necessary – extend existing standards such as Common Information Model (CIM), Systems Modelling Language (SysML) etc., and
- Automation of configuration management, applied to the interconnection of domain-specific simulators in a co-simulation, to the interconnection of real-time entities, and to the automation of multi-RI laboratory experiments.

The objective of this task is thus to surpass the existing level of proficiency in linking together various non-real-time simulators, real-time simulators, Hardware in the Loop (HIL) components, and physical laboratory equipment. Expansion of these domains is necessary to enable testing that encompasses multiple test infrastructures, multiple domains, and/or involves communication-based on messages. The task is specifically designed to showcase the co-simulation of physical infrastructures spanning multiple domains with varying time scales. It will develop and exhibit methods for coupling real-time simulators with co-simulation and HIL to support remote and distributed experiments.

Additionally, it will integrate and standardise the representation of message passing and communicating processes in remote HIL, real-time simulation, and co-simulation, as well as their combinations. This enables the simulation of hierarchical control systems, peer-to-peer markets, and other intricate and distributed systems where communication between multiple processes cannot be adequately depicted as time-continuous, numerical signals. As the complexity of heterogeneous simulation setups increases, the task also aims to create a joint system description across domains and infrastructures and demonstrate a collection of automated or semi-automated mechanisms for configuration management. This will alleviate the increasingly laborious and error-prone task of establishing, maintaining, documenting, deploying, and reproducing the overall configuration.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of configuration management, with the concept and applications in ERIGrid 2.0. The motivation of configuration management is covered in Section 3 along with its potential use cases. The automated configuration of data exchange for multi-RI experiments with the proposed configuration management approach is presented in Section 4. For understanding the configuration management in the scope of ERIGrid 2.0, Section 5 provides a document and user guide. The reference implementation of the existing laboratory coupling tools is introduced in Section 6 of this report. Finally, conclusions and future work are provided in Section 7.

2 Configuration Management Overview

2.1 Concept and Objectives

The United States (US) Department of Energy (DoE) defines that Configuration Management (CM) as an integrated management process ensuring that (*Configuration Management*, 2003):

- The physical and functional arrangement of configuration items whose failure could lead to unacceptable consequences – meet requirements throughout the life of the facility, activity, process, or experiment, and
- Key documentation such as procedures or drawings that may influence conformance with requirements is accurate.

On the other hand, following IEEE 828-2012, i.e., the standard for CM in systems and software engineering (*IEEE Standard for Configuration Management in Systems and Software Engineering*, 2012), CM is a discipline applying technical and administrative direction and surveillance with the objectives to:

- Identify and document the functional and physical characteristics of a configuration item,
- Control changes to those characteristics,
- Record and report change processing and implementation status,
- Verify compliance with specified requirements, and
- Support the audit of the products, results, services, or components to verify conformance to requirements.

In addition, CM is at the core of, and offers essential services to, all the key processes of systems and software engineering, as shown in Figure 1. Detailed explanations of these processes, along with higher-level descriptions of CM, are provided in ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207:2008 (*IEEE/ISO/IEC Systems and software engineering – Requirements for acquirers and suppliers of user documentation*, 2008) and ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2008 (*ISO/IEC/IEEE International Standard – Systems and software engineering System life cycle processes*, 2008).

Figure 1: Life cycle processes that Configuration Management supports (IEEE Standard for Configuration Management in Systems and Software Engineering, 2012).

2.2 Considerations for ERIGrid 2.0

In ERIGrid 2.0, one of the CM functions aims to plan and register certain configuration solutions for an experiment, e.g., how to identify configuration items. At the CEA Smart Grid Laboratory environment, the configuration item normally consists of both hardware and software items. Therefore, it is needed to decide at which level we are going to control these items. For example, in CEA, with hardware items, it can be chosen from among the levels shown in Table 1. The software items, at CEA Smart Grid Lab, include application programs, database management systems, and test tools.

Table 1: Hardware levels for Configuration Management in CEA.

Name	Definition	CEA Smart Grid Lab Hardware
System	A combination of parts, assemblies, etc., joined together to perform an operational function or functions.	Smart Grid Laboratory
Subsystem	A combination of sets, groups, etc., that performs an operational function within, and is a major division of, a system.	Microgrid Benchmark Setup
Set	A unit or units and necessary assemblies, sub-assemblies, and parts connected or associated together to perform an operational function.	PV system
Group	A collection of units, assemblies, or sub-assemblies that is a subdivision of a set or system, but is not capable of performing a complete operational function.	Solar inverter
Unit	An assembly or any combination of parts, sub-assemblies and assemblies mounted together, normally capable of independent operation in a variety of situations	Solar inverter controller
Assembly	A number of parts or sub-assemblies (or any combination thereof), joined together to perform a specific function.	MPPT system
Sub-assembly	One piece (or two or more joined together pieces) not normally subject to disassembly without destroying or impairing the part's designated use.	A printed board of MPPT controller
Part	one piece (or two or more joined together pieces) not normally subject to disassembly without destroying or impairing the part's designated use.	A processor chip

One application example for CM implementation in ERIGrid 2.0 project is simulation setup automation, which is applied for a test case shown in Figure 2 and includes several steps to apply as below

1. Identify the applications
 - Power system protection (anti-islanding in Figure 2), CVC, frequency coordination, etc.
2. Application description: power system architectures
 - Involvement from the related research infrastructures

- Power system models (Simulink, OPAL-RT, PowerFactory, etc.)
- Equipment (Cables, amplifiers, loads, inverters, etc.)
- System configuration

3. System setup

- Establish electrical connection
 - Identify the type of electrical coupling: AC, DC or hybrid
 - Identify the type of electrical signal coupling: synchronous or asynchronous
 - Identify the required signal that is to be exchanged: signal names, unit (SI), scaling and orientation (+/-)
- Establish communication links
 - Identify all the required IP addresses
 - Are the IP addresses reachable externally?: Allow external reachability with help from the IT department.
 - Are the parameters exchanged received correctly?: Check standards, units, and configuration of input/output data system used.

4. Identify the user-case scenarios

- Parameters sweep (CIM script)
- Uncertainty analysis (Stochastic approach)

5. Test management

- Automation
 - Based on the CM method developed in ERIGrid 2.0
 - Documentation standard: ATML (Automatic Test Markup Language), ATML/TD (Test Description), etc.
 - Implementation languages: XML, etc.
- Data logging
 - Different time-referencing protocol: IRIG-B, GPS, IEEE 1588 for data time-synchronisation
 - Mechanism for logging data: generate a report, log to the database or store raw data for offline processing
- Data analysis
 - Collect and verify the test results with stability and accuracy criteria

Figure 2: An example of test case for Configuration Management application.

3 Motivation, Narratives, and Potential Use Cases

3.1 Experiences from ERIGrid

The work in ERIGrid 2.0 builds on previous experiences in the first ERIGrid project which introduced experiments involving multiple RIs (“multi-RI experiment”) in a variety of different configurations (Strasser et al., 2018). This included the real-time coupling of multiple geographically distributed physical laboratories as well as the coupling of physical laboratories with different types of simulators running in real-time (*D-JRA3.1 Simulator Coupling and Smart Grid Libraries*, 2017), primarily in Power Hardware in the Loop (PHIL) and Controller Hardware in the Loop (CHIL) configurations.

During the demonstration phase of ERIGrid, the experience was gathered with the implementation of closed-loop interconnections of RIs across organisational boundaries. One of the main insights gained in the process was that many of the problems encountered are fundamentally non-technical in nature, and stem primarily from the meeting of different organisations, procedures and their underlying assumptions.

While the general concept of RI interconnection could be demonstrated successfully in ERIGrid, no structured process for establishing experimental setups across organisational boundaries was developed. Instead, the necessary adjustments and adaptations were primarily implemented on the go and as needs arose. This de-facto ad-hoc approach resulted in a number of obstacles which became apparent during the experiments and were exacerbated by the need to agree on further laboratory time slots between multiple organisations. These obstacles included:

- While a technical solution for the exchange of signals between RIs was developed, a significant amount of time and manual labour had to be spent on harmonising the mutual interpretation of signal *content* across RIs. The mapping between globally agreed signal labels and their respective local counterparts turned out to be a continuous source of confusion. Similarly, signal units, sign conventions, and scaling factors, as well as the ranges of expected values and the representations of an invalid signal, resulted in lengthy debugging efforts, the need for many repeated experiments and sliding time schedules.
- Repeating physical multi-RI experiments after some time period, or continuing an on-going test after a pause, was found to be significantly more challenging than doing the same within a single laboratory infrastructure. The added complexity arises from the need for reproducing completely identical conditions across multiple smart grid laboratories with many Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), each with a potentially large parameter space, which are used – and potentially reconfigured – by other user groups.
- There are two fundamental options for recording data such as measurements during a geographically distributed experiment: Sending all data to a central logger in real-time or recording data on each site in a distributed manner. While the first approach may often meet technical limitations (e.g., due to bandwidth restrictions), the second approach poses a particular challenge related to merging the individual site logs into one combined log. Besides the technical issue of assuring identical clock references throughout the whole experiment (which is out of the scope of this task), an issue of *data interpretation* arises if data labels, units etc. do not derive from a joint configuration effort. This issue is in many ways symmetrical to that of the signal configuration described above.

None of these obstacles are impossible to overcome, neither do they form intractable problems.

However, in the absence of a systematic procedure, they have proven to result in a lot of manual, error-prone and tedious effort, exacerbated by the geographical distance between participants.

3.2 Case Narratives and Potential Use Cases

In the initial phase of this task, the working group found the above problem definition to be too abstract to propose concrete solutions. In an intermediate step, the following case narratives were developed in order to concretise the problem. They have been subdivided into two fundamental problem groups:

1. The management of static configurations, in order to convey pre-existing knowledge about a facility (e.g., a connectivity model), and
2. The management of dynamic configurations, in order to track the variable configuration aspects of a system (e.g., which part of the grid was a device connected to at a given point in time?).

3.2.1 Static Configuration Narratives

The identified static configuration narratives for ERIGrid 2.0 are:

- An experiment has been conducted in RI1, and measurement data has been recorded. In the years afterwards, the facility has been expanded and modified several times. Several years later, a researcher at RI2 wants to work with the recorded data and needs to know the physical configuration of RI1 at the time of the recording, in order to interpret the data correctly (Where was 'measurement point ABC123' and what was the impedance of the grid connection at the time?).
- A researcher at RI1 has written an adaptive state estimator which is to be tested against multiple RIs RI2 ... RI_n. Providing the exact system configuration of RI2 ... RI_n to the state estimator by hand is a tedious process prone to errors, false assumptions and misunderstandings. A more automated process would simplify the execution of the tests.

3.2.2 Dynamic Configuration Narratives

The identified dynamic configuration narratives for ERIGrid 2.0 are:

- A mobile load unit can be connected at several points of the RI1 grid. During a multi-RI experiment where a controller at RI2 remotely operates RI1, the test is repeated in different configurations where the mobile unit is connected at different points of the grid. When evaluating the data after the testing session, something seems off, and RI2 wants to validate that the mobile unit was connected according to the testing plan.
- A researcher at RI1 has written an adaptive state demand response controller which can operate with different load portfolios. The controller is to be tested against a changing configuration at RI2 where load units are added to or removed from a base configuration at run time, in order to verify the correct response of the controller. The controller, therefore, needs to receive information about the configuration changes in real-time.

3.2.3 Potential Use Cases

During a session at a technical workshop in Vienna, Austria, in October 2022, the above narratives were used as input for four working groups which resulted in the following use cases:

1. *Use Case 1 – Global signal configuration*: Automated configuration of signals and signal properties for the exchange of data between multiple RIs. This case would involve an offline component, globally defining the data flows between RIs, and an online component which performs an automated mapping of the global description to local signal maps, in order to auto-configure all components involved in the data exchange.
2. *Use Case 2 – Automated recording and restoration of laboratory configurations*: Recording of experiment configurations and experiment execution to improve the repeatability of experiments. This case would involve a mechanism for extracting configuration data from laboratory equipment and reconfiguring said equipment. Due to the great variety of automation levels and platforms between RIs, a high degree of modularity would be required to accommodate the entire range from fully automatic to fully manual procedures.
3. *Use Case 3 – Experiment sequencing*: Synchronisation of experiment execution between multiple RIs. This case would involve an offline component which allows for the description of experiment phases, events or states ahead of time, and an online component which synchronises experiment events, phases or states between RIs, and records events, phases or states for documentation.

3.3 Selected Use Case for ERIGrid 2.0

With respect to the limited amount of software development resources available in the task, *Use Case 2* was considered unachievable due to the need for every partner to develop a backend to their particular automation platform. *Use Case 3* was considered to be more closely aligned with the goals of the distributed middleware developments.

Finally, *Use Case 1* was selected as the case with the lowest amount of software development knowledge required across partners. Furthermore, this use case aligns closely with existing activities such as the Universal Application Programming Interface (uAPI).

In the following sections a description of the selected solution approach for the selected *Use Case 1* is provided.

4 Configuration Management Approach

The major focus of the proposed CM is the automated configuration of data exchange for multi-RI experiments. This involves the following:

- An offline global configuration/description of data flows between the participating RIs, and
- An online automated mapping of local RI signals to data channels for the experiment, based on the global description.

The proposed CM is shown in Figure 3 with two example RIs conducting a joint experiment. This is achieved through a dedicated laboratory coupling tool, such as Virtually Interconnected Laboratories for Large systems Simulation/emulation (VILLAS) Framework, Joint Test Facility for Smart Energy Networks with Distributed Energy Resources (JaNDER), or Lablink. These tools serve as a vehicle for data-exchange between the RIs. However, as outlined in the previous section, the configuration of these tools is non-trivial, manual, and error prone.

Figure 3: Overview of ERIGrid 2.0's Configuration Management approach.

To overcome this, a CM tool is proposed which has a primary goal of automating the process of configuring data exchange for experiments involving multiple RIs. This is accomplished by creating an offline global configuration or description of how data will flow between the participating RIs. Additionally, an online automated mapping of local RI signals to data channels for the experiment is created based on the global description. With this approach, the CM process can be greatly streamlined, leading to easier and reproducible multi-RI experiments.

4.1 Global Experiment Configuration

The global experimental configuration, as the name suggests is a file which defines global facets of a multi-RI experiment. It is a crucial component in the automation of multi-RI experiments and is developed as a structured and machine-readable file that describes various aspects of the experiment, such as:

- List of channels,
- Signal list, and
- Type of transport.

In addition to these, the file can also include other pertinent experimental information such as the participating RIs, the lab setups, and other experiment parameters. By having a comprehensive and standardised global experimental configuration file, the automation process can be made more efficient and effective, allowing for seamless and reliable data exchange between the different RIs involved in the experiment. Furthermore, the global experimental configuration file can also be used to facilitate the reproducibility of experiments, as it provides a clear and detailed record of the experimental setup and parameters. Hence, such a file can make it easier to configure joint experiments between participating RIs.

An example global configuration Yet Another Markup Language (YAML) file is described by the code snippet in Listing 1. The subsequent section provides a detailed explanation of each part of the configuration file.

Listing 1: Example global configuration.

```

1  nodes:
2    rwth:
3      description: RWTH Aachen University
4
5      uapi_endpoint: http://uapi.dtu.dk:8080/v2 # Optional
6
7      channels: # This node provides (sources) these channels
8      - id: rwth::busbar1:v
9        unit: V
10       rate: 100.0
11
12     - { id: rwth::ch1.v, unit: V, rate: 100.0 }
13     - { id: rwth::ch2.v, unit: V, rate: 100.0 }
14
15     transport:
16       type: jander
17
18       # All following attributes are specific to the type of transport
19       # and not covered by the global config schema.
20       redis:
21         host: 10.10.2.1
22         port: 123
23         username: erigrd
24         password: wdsjfsd
25
26     ait:
27       transport:
28         type: lablink
29
30       # All following attributes are specific to the type of transport
31       # and not covered by the global config schema.
32       client-type: opal-rt
33
34       mapping:
35       - channel: rwth::busbar1:v
36         simulink_signal_name:
37
38     connections:
39     - from: rwth::busbar1:v
40       to: dtu
41     - from: rwth::busbar1:v
42       to: ait
43
44     ri_adapters:
45     - type: syslab
46
47     nodes:
48     - ait
49     - rwth

```

4.2 Application Workflow

The workflow to apply the proposed CM tool is outlined in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Configuration management workflow.

5 Configuration Description

The purpose of the configuration is two-fold. The first is for coupling real, simulated, and emulated components and devices from different RIs seamless. This allows an automated configuration of data flows between RIs. The second is that every RI involved in the tests is able to configure its electric components and communication networks in order to run the tests. Although each RI has a different methodology for this second purpose, this global CM is an input to perform this task.

5.1 Document

The document consists of the following parts.

5.1.1 RI Nodes

The RIs involved in the testing scenarios must be listed first. It is a list of RIs containing an entry per RI. The RI node must specify how many devices and points (channels) will be used.

5.1.2 Devices

This is a list of the RI' devices used in the scenario. Notice that this list is not mandatory because the naming conventions of the channels implicitly include them.

5.1.3 Channels

Following the uAPI terminology, the list of the channels (measurements, setpoints, states, commands and events) which will be accessed in the tests are identified by their Identifications (IDs) according to the naming conventions. The channels are grouped by the RIs they belong to and they also can include extra information such as the units, scale, datatype, rate, etc.

5.1.4 Transports

The transport used by the RIs shall be defined in this section. The uAPI can be used for this purpose, whose self-descriptive channels are understood by all RIs. However, if an RI specific transport wanted to be used (VILLASframework, JaNDER, Lablink, etc.), this section shall include the configuration elements, parameters, attributes, etc. needed for a successful communication.

5.1.5 Data Flow

The data flow defines the connections and the direction between the defined RI's channels. Therefore, the samples (measurements) of a channel of one RI can be redirected to one or more RIs, allowing to send samples or set setpoints between RIs. The data flow also establishes the allowed RIs which shall access to a specific channel in the tests. The data flow

section does not care about transport, type of data, streaming, etc. It is just a map of channels between different RIs, granting permissions between RIs and channels.

5.2 Usage

5.2.1 Experiment Configuration

A multi-RI experiment consists in a sort of devices, algorithms, emulators, etc. from different locations running as a unique laboratory. It begins with a provided state, which has to be sent to the RIs to configure the scenario and coordinate the grid. Once set, the experiment is run, collecting data and setting setpoints from/to different channels, performing any action. The experiment execution demands continuous channel monitoring and coordination. When the test is finished, the data shall be available to be analysed.

For example, a test can be a scenario with one Alternating Current (AC) line connected to several loads, batteries, distributed generators like Photovoltaic (PV), etc. from different RIs. When a reactive load is switched on in RI1, the reactive power in its electric line will change. Therefore, such data (e.g., VAr) must be notified to all other RIs in order to reproduce the same line state.

To define a test, the user must convert the conceptual idea into a CM document. It can be done following these steps, which can be guided by a software/tool:

1. Identify which devices are needed for the test.
2. Find out which RIs have the required devices (real, emulated, or simulated), adding them as RI nodes.
3. Find out which channels are needed, without routing. This step is to know if the device provides a channel required by the test or not (e.g., if the test needs the Power Factor of a line, check that the RI has its available channel).
4. Add all data flows between channels according to the test.
5. At this step, a graph of the test can be done by parsing the configuration file, which can help the user to check whether the test complies with the conceptual idea or not. An example is depicted in Figure 5. The previous steps can be done without Information Technology (IT) knowledge.
6. For each RI:
 - (a) Select the transport to be used, and
 - (b) Select the needed parameters for the transport: Internet Protocol (IP), ports, credentials, etc.

After these steps, the global configuration file for the test is defined. It will be used for the CM, as depicted in Figure 3, to configure the laboratory coupling tool, as well as the RI local configuration described below. This file ensures not only the repeatability of the test at any time, but it also makes easier the RI substitution.

Figure 5: Global configuration management file creation.

5.2.2 RI Local Configuration

The global configuration file is also an input for every RI local configuration, which will set up the parameters to run the applications, configure their transports and prepare the communication networks.

Application Configuration

The RI extracts its channels and transport sections from the global configuration file in order to prepare the internal infrastructure of the test:

- Extracts the transport used by the RI,
- Extracts and reserves all (input) ports where the RI will receive messages,
- Configures the (output) channels which will be used to send data, including endpoints, ports, credentials, etc.,
- Maps the (input/output) channels to the internal infrastructure (channels, databases, etc.), and
- Set up the flow of the channels by configuring the routing paths.

Communications Setup

The RI must enable the communications for sending and receiving data from/to other RIs. This means opening ports, granting access to some IP (or Domain Name System (DNS) names) and set up any cybersecurity methods (credentials, client/server certificates, etc.) which are also present in the global configuration file.

From the data flow, input and output channels to other RIs can be collected. Such data is useful for the RI cybersecurity policies and rules:

- Grant access to send data (addresses, ports and protocols) to other RIs,
- Grant access to receive data from RIs (ports and protocols) using the RI application/-transport, and
- Blocking access to all other RIs present in the global configuration which do not communicate with this RI.

6 Reference Implementation

In the following section, reference implementations of the CM for the coupling tools VILLASnode, JaNDER, and Lablink are described.

6.1 VILLASnode

VILLASnode is a flexible gateway for co-simulation interface data. It converts protocols, (de-)multiplexes signals to and from multiple sources and destinations. Currently, around 18 different protocols and interfaces are supported, ranging from general purpose broker-based messaging protocols like AMQP and MQTT, over IEC 61850, to web protocols like WebSockets or FIWARE NGSI and many more. It collects statistics about the exchanged data such as packet loss, one-way delay, and jitter and provides a network emulation to simulate the conditions of a geographically distributed co-simulation. VILLASnode is a C/C++ application optimised for Real-time Linux operating systems using PREEMPT_RT patch. VILLASnode is part of the VILLASframework toolset, whose main architecture is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Overview of the VILLASframework architecture.

The basic function of VILLASnode is to provide an intermediate representation of the simulation data for a single point in time. The data structure consists of an array of floats and meta-data such as timestamps and sequence numbers. VILLASnode does not schedule time steps between simulators and each Real-time Simulator (RTS) runs according to their own system clock. The simulation data is transferred between connected nodes asynchronously (Vogel, Mirz, Razik, & Monti, 2017). Additionally, VILLASframework provides other tools like:

- *VILLASweb*: It provides a web-based backend configuration and visualisation tool, and
- *VILLAScontroller*: It enables a global control of all connected nodes/RTSs irrespective of manufacturer and it distributes command and status messages.

VILLASnode currently supports the uAPI v2 and, like in the case of JaNDER, would require the uAPI specification to define the creation of new channels to facilitate the integration with a (semi)automated configuration management tool. On the other hand, VILLASnode could be extended with a tool that automatically generates the associated local configuration file using the global configuration file.

Moreover, VILLASnode could be used in further research activities in ERIGrid 2.0 related to the distributed middleware for extended services for integrated real-time and non-real-time environments and simulation setup automation, respectively. While the reference implementation such VILLASnode exists for interconnecting laboratories and collaborating research works, a guideline for distributed test configurations with multi RIs is required especially lessons learned from implementation in practice, for example cybersecurity requirements for the external interface.

Simulation setup with associated configurations between RIs differ depending on the use cases and involved other stakeholders, i.e., IT architecture of each laboratory but yet no documentation or best practice on how to automate this simulation setup and operation processes in an automated manner which could save time and enhance efficient and secure interfaces between RIs. In addition, real-time exchange information between RIs is essential. Identifying foreseeable uncertainties of distributed simulations to improve information exchange could be tested like time delay and time synchronisation between RIs. An approach(s) with automated solutions for simulation setup and configurations are highly needed for RIs connection management.

6.2 JaNDER

JaNDER is a communication platform developed within ERIGrid that allows data to be exchanged between different RIs. Using JaNDER, data is exchanged by means of a secure internet connection using the Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS).

JaNDER's core functionality is the replication of infrastructure data through a cloud node. When data is recorded in a local database, it is mirrored in the cloud database and vice versa. At this level, the data is simply transported without any interpretation of its structure. On top of this replication software it is possible to build a layer where the data model describing the exchanged measurements is defined. This layer is responsible to expose the data model chosen to exchange data that can be custom or based on existing standards (e.g., IEC 61850/61970). As example, this layer makes the data model developed for the distributed middleware in ERIGrid 2.0 accessible to the user and maps the model class instances to the appropriate database data structures that need to be replicated. The architecture is depicted in Figure 7.

The building blocks of JaNDER are described below:

- *Cloud Node*: Redis database¹ in the cloud, serving as a platform for exchanging data between the various RI nodes. Access to the cloud node is secured using certificates and HTTPS protocol. It acts as the intermediary between the local nodes of the different RI instances.
- *RI Database*: A Redis database located at the facility that serves as the endpoint for data read and write operations. The replication software, if running, synchronises the data between the cloud and the local nodes.

¹<https://redis.io>

Figure 7: JaNDER transport equipped with the uAPI; each RI is equipped with a local database instance connected to the cloud node.

- *Replication Software*: Developed in Golang², the software opens connections to both the local Redis node and the cloud node using secure certificates. It replicates data between the two nodes by subscribing to the Redis keyspace notifications and intercepting updates of keys matching a specific pattern. The replication can be conducted bidirectionally between local and remote nodes.
- *Universal Application Programming Interface Middleware*: This component exposes the ERIGrid 2.0 Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and communicates with the local Redis node by reading and writing information. The data model underlying the API is mapped to Redis keys for replication to the cloud node and accessibility across connected infrastructures.

Once a JaNDER instance is installed and configured within the RI, measurements can be written on the local Redis instance in order to be shared with other RIs via the cloud node. The parameters needed for the replication via the cloud node are the following:

- *Certificates*: are needed to perform the connection to the cloud node, and
- *Namespace*: this parameter is needed to group all the measures involved in an experiment/simulation.

At present, the implementation of the APIs enables the use of channels, samples, and events as specified in ERIGrid 2.0's distributed laboratory middleware (*D-JRA3.1 Distributed Laboratory Middleware*, 2023). The current definition of the API does not foresee the creation of channels but with an extension it should allow the channels configuration to be launched at the initialisation of JaNDER. The current implementation of the API enables JaNDER

²<https://go.dev>

to operate in various infrastructures, with compatibility and interaction with different transport services still under development.

6.3 Lablink for Simulation Message-Bus Based Solutions

In this section, an implementation of the Lablink tool as a software package based on the Simulation Message Bus (SMB) idea is presented (Nguyen et al., 2020). In this regard, Lablink, a communication middleware intentionally created for the purpose, facilitates the quick and easy connection between software and hardware elements. Its primary function is to enable various devices present in an electric power laboratory (such as power sources, loads, grid emulators, or measurement devices) to establish a bidirectional data and control signal flow. The fundamental structure of Lablink, which can be used for both real-time and non real-time simulation, is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Lablink structure for real-time and non real-time applications. (Nguyen et al., 2020)

As in Figure 8, the left part focuses on N offline simulation tasks, where time step sizes fall within the range of $t_{S,O_i} \in [100\text{ms}; 2\text{s}]$. These tasks are connected to the Lablink structure in an autonomous and bidirectional manner for signal and data exchange. The specific range of time step sizes can vary greatly depending on the type of offline simulation being performed. However, typical values for simulation setups related to electrical investigations are proposed in Figure 8. As depicted in the SMB architecture illustrated in Figure 8, Lablink handles incoming and outgoing data from offline simulation tasks and the linked Digital Real-Time Simulation (DRTS), respectively.

In this scenario, the sample rates for Lablink are specified as minimum time step sizes of $t_{S,LL} = 1$ ms. However, the real-time computing system has fixed time step sizes, owing to the inherent constraints of real-time simulation. For CHIL applications, the DRTS usually operates with a time step size ranging from $t_{S,RTi} \in [100\text{ns}; 1\text{ms}]$. Simulation tasks that emulate Pulse-width Modulation (PWM) signals for control applications require sample rates of less than $1 \mu\text{s}$. On the other hand, the real-time machine on the right-hand side of this figure is connected to one or more interface boards. These interface boards serve as functional units between the machine

controller implemented in hardware and the DRTS system. The number of signals exchanged between the controller and the DRTS can be significant and typically exceeds the number of signals exchanged between offline tasks and Lablink in typical CHIL applications related to converter control simulations. The maximum specified time step size for the controller interface, denoted by $t_{S,CI}$, is limited to 10 μs .

7 Conclusions and Future Work

7.1 Achievements

This report summarised the activities undertaken as part of the CM. An overview of the CM was provided, to motivate the need for a standardised approach. Subsequently, the proposed CM approach was outlined. It consists of a global experiment configuration file that serves as a semi-automated mechanism for CM in multi-RI experiments. Furthermore, the details of such a file were provided, alongside reference implementations. Thereby, through this approach, documentation and reproducibility of joint experiments are significantly improved.

7.2 Follow-up Activities

The tasks undertaken in this work are intricately interconnected with and will significantly contribute to numerous other objectives within the overarching scope of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. The work carried out in this report not only serves as an essential building block for the successful completion of various other tasks, but also plays a pivotal role in achieving the overall goals and outcomes of the ERIGrid 2.0 initiative. The close interdependence between this work and the wider project highlights the integrated nature of the research efforts, emphasising the collaborative and synergistic approach employed in ERIGrid 2.0.

First of all, feedback from various sources, including this work, the work related to the enhanced validation methods within the ERIGrid 2.0 project, as well as external contributions from the Horizon 2020 (H2020) SmILES project, which employed elements of the ERIGrid Holistic Testing Procedure (HTD) for its own objectives, will inform the development of the HTD extension in ERIGrid 2.0. Building on this feedback, the HTD extension will strive to establish a unified framework for holistic testing, encompassing diverse tasks such as traditional lab experiments, cross-RI configurations, up and out scaling, simulations, and more. Furthermore, a compilation of “best practice applications” will be curated, serving as a proof-of-concept and reference for users. This collective effort aims to harmonise the holistic testing procedure and provide a consistent approach for a wide range of applications within ERIGrid 2.0.

Secondly, this work is also closely link to the distributed laboratory middleware development in ERIGrid 2.0. This relationship is presented in Figure 9. It has been proven through previous experience that deploying integrated remote testing setups requires additional services that may not be directly related to the main function of data transfer, but can greatly impact the amount of effort needed to carry out a remote test. Thus, Joint Research Activity (JRA) JRA3.3 aims to deal with these problem by extending services for integrated real-time and non-real-time environments. In JRA2.3 (i.e., this work), a joint description format and determines practical ways to locally automate the exchange of configuration information with individual RI components has been established while JRA3.3 will develop a mechanism for exchanging this information between RIs.

By accomplishing the two tasks, it will be possible to tackle the configuration issues associated with distributed tests. This involves developing a reliable approach for supplying distributed simulators and RI components with essential items such as project files, parameters, etc., in a consistent and test-oriented manner. Furthermore, the outcomes of this work will be served as an important input for JRA3.4 in ERIGrid 2.0. The objectives of JRA3.4 is to enable all the ERIGrid 2.0 RI elements with a machine-to-machine interface to be operated in an as-automated fashion as possible, which allows batch-scripted optimisation tasks or parameter

sweeps to test a certain setup against a given standard.

Figure 9: The relationship between this work and the distributed laboratory middleware in ERIGrid 2.0.

Therefore, the configuration approach proposed in this task will be implemented in JRA3.4. The developed CM will enhance tools developed in JRA3.4 for RI connection management (register all required parts, test the setup, etc.), automation (scripting of simulation configuration and runs), auto logging (time-synchronised collection of measurement data) and scenario handling (cross-RI test-case configuration management). The relationship between this work and JRA3.4 is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10: The relationship between this work (i.e., JRA2.3) and JRA3.4 in ERIGrid 2.0.

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